

Mechanistic studies on the reactions of iodopentaammineruthenium(III) complex cation and thiocyanate ion in aqueous solution

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Manuscript received 14 July 1998, accepted 8 December 1998

The substitution of iodide ion by thiocyanate ion in the iodopentaammineruthenium(III) complex cation in aqueous solution has been investigated at 35–50°. Rate increases linearly with thiocyanate ion concentration having a positive intercept on the rate axis. The intercept gives the aquation rate constant of the iodo complex, and the slope represents thiocyanate anation rate. The rate was compared with the thiocyanate anation rate of the aqua complex by making a separate study between the two species. The second order thiocyanate anation rates and activation parameters for the process are close in the two processes but a difference in mechanism exists between the two. Thiocyanate anation reaction follows an associative interchange mechanism.

Anation reactions are utilised in the syntheses of a number of desired ruthenium(II)/(III) complexes^{1,2}. Anation reactions of chloro- and bromopentaammineruthenium(III) complexes with thiocyanate ion in aqueous medium have been reported³. In these complex ions, substitution of thiocyanate ion takes place by a 'dissociative interchange' mechanism through the formation of the aqua intermediate complex. The product primarily contains the nitrogen bonded thiocyanatopentaammine complex. Chloride and bromide ions are hard bases and ruthenium(III) is only a moderately hard acid. However, when these chloride and bromide ions are replaced by iodide ion, (which is a soft base) its replacement in anation reaction by the ambident ligand thiocyanate ion may reveal interesting results as the thiocyanate ion may behave both as a moderately hard or moderately soft base depending upon its linkage sites as nitrogen or sulphur atoms⁴. In order to compare these substitution reactions with anation of aquapentaammine complex by the thiocyanate ion, we have also incorporated this study in the present investigation.

Results and Discussion

Rate constants as obtained from Guggenheim's plot for the iodopentaammine and the aquapentaammineruthenium(III) complexes are given in Table 1. The rate increases linearly with thiocyanate concentration for both the complexes. However, for the iodopentaammine complex the plot has a positive intercept on rate axis while the intercept is zero in the case of the aquapentaammine complex. The rate expression for the iodo complex may be expressed as

$$\text{Rate} = k_1 [\text{complex}] + k_2 [\text{complex}] [\text{SCN}^-] \quad (1)$$

$$k_{\text{obs}} = k_1 + k_2 [\text{SCN}^-] \quad (2)$$

and for the aqua complex, it is

$$\text{Rate} = k_3 [\text{complex}] [\text{SCN}^-] \quad (3)$$

$$k_{\text{obs}} = k_3 [\text{SCN}^-] \quad (4)$$

where, k_1 is the rate constant for the SCN^- free path and k_2 and k_3 are rate constants for SCN^- dependent paths. The values of derived rate constants are given in Table 2 along with the corresponding activation parameters.

Table 1. Observed rate constants ($10^4 k, \text{s}^{-1}$) for the reaction between $[\text{Ru}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{X}]^{2+/3+}$ and SCN^- ($\text{X} = \text{I}^-$ or H_2O)*

X	Temp. °C	$[\text{NH}_4\text{SCN}]$ mol dm ⁻³	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.05	0.1	0.2
I ⁻	35		1.0	1.7	2.0	2.90	5.40	10.40
	40		1.17	2.0	2.6	3.55	6.34	11.95
	45		1.62	2.4	3.2	4.46	7.02	13.24
	50		2.0	2.83	4.02	5.81	8.02	14.88
H ₂ O	35		0.3	0.62	0.94	1.48	2.90	6.10
	40		0.5	1.00	1.53	2.40	4.82	9.92
	45		0.73	1.45	2.39	3.65	7.00	13.26
	50		1.04	1.98	3.17	5.02	10.06	19.24

*Error, < 3%.

Rate constant versus thiocyanate ion concentration plot does not show any deviation from linearity up to the highest concentration of the ligand (0.2 mol dm⁻³) studied. Ion-pair formation does not seem to play role at any stage of the reaction. Above 55°, deviation from unimolecular rate plot indicates a complicated form of the reaction that takes place at this stage. Prasad *et al.*⁵ observed the formation of a number of products above 55°. At the experimental temperature range (30–50°), uniform first order plot was obtained for

Table 2. Rate constants and activation parameters for the reaction of complexes via SCN⁻ independent (k_1) and SCN⁻ dependent (k_2 or k_3) paths

Compd.	35°	40°	45°	50°	ΔH^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS^\ddagger JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
Ru(NH ₃) ₅ I ²⁺						
10 ⁴ k_1 , s ⁻¹	0.80 ± 0.03	0.87 ± 0.03	1.00 ± 0.05	1.16 ± 0.05	25 ± 5	-196 ± 12
10 ⁴ k_2 , mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	41.2 ± 1	54.2 ± 2	72.00 ± 2	98.00 ± 2	94 ± 4	7 ± 4
Ru(NH ₃) ₅ H ₂ O ³⁺						
10 ⁴ k_3 mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	38 ± 1	51.2 ± 1	73.2 ± 1.5	87.00 ± 1	96 ± 4	15 ± 4

the initial two hours, but the spectra does not match with that of the thiocyanatopentaammine complex⁶ as observed in the case of chloro and bromo complexes at 55–70° range. At this stage a complex with three ruthenium centre is formed⁵. However, at higher temperature (>65°) the trimeric product gives the monomeric product. The rate constant of the thiocyanate independent path obtained from the intercept of 'rate' versus thiocyanate concentration plot, virtually represents aquation of the halo complex in the case of chloro and bromo complexes; but it is much greater than the aquation rate constant of the iodopentaammine complex. At 40° the rate constant for the thiocyanate independent path is $8.7 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$ while that of the aquation of the iodo complex is $0.26 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$ ⁷. Activation parameter values also differ from aquation values⁷. By simple reasoning, the intercept does not represent aquation of the pentaammine complex to aquapentaammine species but to some other form of the aquated product. The anating ambidentate ligand thiocyanate with more than one bonding site plays the major role in bringing three ruthenium ions together to form the trimeric product [Ru₃(NH₃)₁₃(SCN)I₂](SCN)₆. During this process it acts somewhat like a bridging ligand in bringing two or three complex molecules together. Whether the anation proceeds via the formation of the aquapentaammine species was tested by carrying out the anation reaction of the aqua complex with thiocyanate ion. Nevertheless, the rate constants obtained in the two cases are different. The anation step in the substitution process of the iodopentaammine complex does not involve the aquapentaammine species. The final product formed with the aquapentaammine complex was the nitrogen bonded [Ru(NH₃)₅SCN]²⁺ species. The derived second order rate constants for thiocyanate anation reaction (k_2 and k_3) of the two complexes does not differ much. The spectral scanning pattern has also much similarity, so there may be some similarity in reaction mechanisms too. As the ion-pair formation has little significance, anation of the aquapentaammine complex proceeds through the associative interchange mechanism which is also the likely process for the substitution of iodide ion by thiocyanate ion.

Bonding site of the incoming ligand thiocyanate ion merits discussion. From electronic and ir spectra of the product complex we could not ascertain the bonding site. Ruthenium(III) is a moderately hard acid and the ligand thiocyanate is relatively more hard when it is linked through nitrogen atom rather than sulphur atom, so it is likely that the bond formation takes place through the nitrogen end. In conclusion, we may say that at the experimental temperature range, the thiocyanate ion replaces iodide ion from the pentaammine complex through the formation of an aquated intermediate in an associative process simultaneously acting as a bridging ligand between the two or three molecules of the complex ion.

Experimental

Iodopentaammineruthenium(III) iodide was prepared by the literature method⁸. Aquapentaammineruthenium(III) perchlorate was prepared *in situ* either in aqueous solution or in the solid state after necessary crystallisation from the aqueous phase by the base hydrolysis of chloropentaammineruthenium(III) chloride. An aqueous solution of the chloro complex was treated with its one-tenth volume of 0.01 mol dm⁻³ NaOH solution at room temperature for 15–20 min and then neutralised with perchloric acid. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 2.5–3.0, where the complex ion exists as the aqua species. It was used as such in solution, otherwise recrystallised after evaporation on a rotary evaporator. Purity of the solid compound was checked by elemental analyses.

p-Toluenesulphonic acid (PTS) and its sodium salt (NaPTS) (E. Merck) were used. Double-distilled water and distilled alcohol were used in the preparation of solutions. All other chemicals were either of A.R. grade or purified by suitable methods.

A Sicospeck spectrophotometer and a SICO were used.

Kinetic measurements and product identification :

The reaction was investigated only over a small range of temperature (35–50°) as beyond this temperature range de-

viation occurred in unimolecular rate plot. The reaction was carried out in the presence of $0.01\text{--}0.2\text{ mol dm}^{-3}\text{ NH}_4\text{SCN}$. Ionic strength (I) was maintained at 0.2 mol dm^{-3} with NaPTS. The iodo complex showed λ_{max} at 545 nm which in the course of reaction (*ca* 2 h) shifted to 500 nm with other bands at 360 and 220 nm. The species responsible for this spectra was identified as $[\text{Ru}_3(\text{NH}_3)_{13}(\text{SCN})\text{I}_2](\text{SCN})_6$. The aquapentaammine complex on similar treatment with thiocyanate ion at the same temperature range showed similar change in spectral pattern, with maxima position shifting from 490 to 496 nm having other bands at 321, 280 and 205 nm. The extinction value at 496 nm changed from near zero to 1000, showing the formation of the thiocyanatopentaammine complex. However, the extinction coefficient of the thiocyanato complex has a much

higher value⁶. So the formation of the thiocyanato complex by the anation reaction is only partial.

References

1. W. A. Kalsbeek and H. H. Thorp, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1994, **33**, 3427.
2. K. B. Reddy, M. P. Cho, J. F. Wishart, T. J. Inge and S. S. Isied, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1996, **35**, 7241.
3. B. Chakravarty and S. Adhikari, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1991, **30**, 692.
4. J. A. Davies and F. R. Hartley, *Chem. Rev.*, 1981, **81**, 79.
5. R. Prasad, S. K. S. Yadav and U. Agarwala, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1981, **43**, 2359.
6. S. W. Lin and A. F. Schreiner, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1971, **5**, 290.
7. J. A. Broomhead and L. Kane-Maguire, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, **7**, 2519.
8. A. D. Allen, F. Bottomley, R. O. Harris, V. P. Rainsalu and C. V. Senoff, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **89**, 5595.